

ISic0279

I.Sicily inscription 0279

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Taormina, Antiquarium del

Teatro Antico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Imp(eratori) · Caes(ari) · div[iSeptimiSeveriPii]
2. Arab(ici) · Adia[beniciParthicimax(imi)]
3. Br[i]ttaniciBritannici · [maximif(ilio)diviM(arci)]
4. Antonini Ḡ[erman(ici)Sarm(atici)nep(oti)]
5. divi · Antoṅ[iniPiipronepoti]
6. divi H[adrianiabnepotidiviTraiani]
7. [etdiviNervaeadnepoti]
8. [M(arco) Aurelio Antonino Pio Fel(ici) Aug(usto)]

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491489

EDCS 21900310

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.6991 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650752>)

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